

ACRIDINE DERIVATIVES. PART V. AUROTHIO- AND ARGENTOTHIO-ACRIDINES.*

BY S. J. DAS-GUPTA.

Gold and silver compounds of 5-thiolacridine derivatives have been described.

It was considered to be of interest to prepare acridine compounds with gold or silver and note their pharmacological activity. For this purpose, 5-thiolacridine derivatives of the type (I, R=H) have been prepared. These thiolacridines, on treatment with potassium auribromide, afford the gold compounds of the type (I, R=Au). The silver compounds of the type (I, R=Ag) are prepared by treating the sodium salts of the thiolacridines with silver nitrate.

The 5-thiolacridine derivatives readily dissolve in sodium hydroxide solution and may be regenerated from these solutions by neutralisation. But the products liberated are lighter in colour than the parent compounds. Recrystallisation or simple heating on a steam-bath transforms them back to the original form. This suggests that most probably the thiolacridine derivatives exist in both thio-ketonic (II) and thio-enolic forms (III).

All the gold and silver compounds are stable and deep red coloured solids having definite melting points. They are insoluble in water and in common organic solvents.

During the preparation of the above aurothioacridines, another set of gold compounds has been isolated possessing a lighter colour. From general properties and the results of analysis, the structure (IV) is assigned to them.

Previous parts of this series of papers appeared under the caption "Acridine derivatives as antimalarials".

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine.—2 : 5-Dichloro-7-methoxyacridine (2 g.) was heated with potassium xanthogenate (4 g.) in phenol (6 g.) at 115° for 3 hours. After cooling, the mixture was poured into ice-cold water, stirred for some time, filtered and washed thoroughly with water, and crystallised from alcohol in deep red shining needles, m.p. 245°. The substance is insoluble in water but soluble in both aqueous and alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution. On acidification of alkaline solution, the thiol compound is precipitated as yellow needles but may be reconverted to the red variety when heated in a steam-oven or when recrystallised from alcohol. The yellow form, admixed with equal part of the red variety, melts at 245° without depression. (Found : N, 4.98 ; S, 11.4. $C_{14}H_{10}ONClS$ requires N, 5.08; S, 11.61 per cent).

2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-aurothiolacridine (Structure analogous to I).—To 0.55 g. of 2-chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine in alcohol (25 c.c.), sulphur dioxide solution (4%, 20 c.c.) was added and the mixture was slowly treated at room temperature with a solution of potassium auribromide (1.2 g.) in alcohol (12 c.c.). The mixture was allowed to stand for several hours with occasional shaking and then diluted with alcohol, filtered, and the product washed thoroughly with alcohol and water. The dark red amorphous substance was dried in *vacuo* over phosphorus pentoxide, m.p. 247-48° (decomp.). It is very sparingly soluble in acetone and insoluble in all other common solvents and could not be further crystallised. It is also insoluble in dilute acids but sparingly soluble in hot and strong hydrochloric and acetic acids. (Found : N, 3.18 ; S, 6.27 ; Au, 43.2. $C_{14}H_9ONClSAu$ requires N, 2.97 ; S, 6.78 ; Au, 41.78 per cent).

Bromoauoro-5-dithio-(2-chloro-7-methoxy)-acridine (Structure analogous to IV).—2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine (crystallised, 0.55 g.) in alcohol (25 c.c.) was treated slowly with a solution of potassium auribromide (0.6 g.) in alcohol (10 c.c.). Sulphur dioxide solution (4%, 6 c.c.) was then added slowly and the mixture left aside for several hours with occasional shaking. After dilution with alcohol, the mixture was filtered, washed thoroughly with alcohol and water. The solid, after being dried in *vacuo*, was obtained as a deep red amorphous substance, m.p. 254-55° (decomp.). It is very sparingly soluble in alcohol and acetone and in all other solvents and dilute acids. [Found : N, 3.44 ; S, 7.88 ; Au, 23.3. ($C_{14}H_9ONClS_2$), AuBr requires N, 3.39 ; S, 7.75 ; Au, 23.85 per cent].

2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-argenthioacridine.—2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine (1.1 g.) was dissolved in dilute alcohol (50 c.c.) containing sodium hydroxide (0.16 g.) and silver nitrate solution (0.75 g. in 10 c.c. of water)

was added slowly with shaking when a precipitate separated out. After a few minutes the solid was collected, washed thoroughly with alcohol and water, and dried in *vacuo*. The dark red amorphous substance, m.p. 290° (decomp.), thus obtained, is almost insoluble in all common solvents and in ammonia and dilute acids but is sparingly soluble in strong acids. (Found : N, 3.54; Ag, 28.26. $C_{14}H_9ONClSAg$ requires N, 3.66; Ag, 28.23 per cent).

7-Methoxy-5-thiolacridine.—7-Methoxy-5-chloroacridine (2 g.) and potassium xanthogenate (4 g.) were heated in phenol (6 g.) at $125-30^{\circ}$ for more than 3 hours. Isolated as described previously, the compound was obtained in red shining needles from alcohol, m.p. $231-32^{\circ}$. (Found : S, 13.07. $C_{14}H_{11}ONS$ requires S, 13.27 per cent). It is insoluble in water but soluble in dilute aqueous or alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution, from which it is liberated on acidification in light yellow form with identical melting point and changes to the red variety when heated in a steam-bath or when recrystallised.

7-Methoxy-5-aurothioacridine.—The above thiolacridine (0.48 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) was mixed with sulphur dioxide solution (20 c.c., 4%) and then slowly treated with an alcoholic solution of potassium auribromide (1.2 g.). Isolated as in the previous case, the compound was obtained as dark red amorphous powder, insoluble in all common solvents, m.p. $219-20^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found : S, 7.01; Au, 46.7. $C_{14}H_{10}ONSAu$ requires S, 7.32; Au, 45.08 per cent).

Bromoauoro-5-dithio-(7-methoxy)-acridine (Structure analogous to IV).—The foregoing thiolacridine (0.48 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) was slowly treated with an alcoholic solution of potassium auribromide (0.6 g.). The mixture was shaken and sulphur dioxide solution (6 c.c., 4%) was slowly added. The compound was isolated as a deep red powder, m.p. $222-23^{\circ}$. [Found : S, 8.45; Au, 27.0. $(C_{14}H_{10}ONS)_2 AuBr$ requires S, 8.25; Au, 26.02 per cent).

7-Methoxy-5-argenthioacridine.—The thiolacridine was dissolved in dilute alcohol containing equivalent proportion of sodium hydroxide and treated with silver nitrate as described. The compound was isolated as brick-red amorphous powder, insoluble in all solvents, m.p. 261° (decomp.). (Found : N, 3.89; Ag, 31.12. $C_{14}H_{10}ONSAg$ requires N, 4.02; Ag, 31.03 per cent).

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RESEARCH LABORATORY,
BENGAL IMMUNITY,
CALCUTTA.

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